

Human Resources Strengthening Model Manager of Sulamadaha Beach Tourist Attraction, Ternate

Fachria Y Marasabessy¹

¹(Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas Terbuka, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT: Human Resources (SDM) plays a role in providing quality services to tourists at a tourist destination. However, this aspect has not been given much attention to by the administrators or the local government. The research focuses on analyzing the model of strengthening SDM in the management of the tourist objects of Sulamadaha Coast City of Ternate. The case study approach is used to explain and structure the construction of the phenomenon studied so that it can produce a model of human resource enhancement strategy that can be used by the parties. Interviews and observations on the Sulamadaha Coast are used as primary data. Studies related to research topics are used for secondary information. The results of this study mapped that the human resources of Sulamadaha Coast managers are still based on local resources of the Survival Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) Suramadaha Beach. So this research produces a model of strengthening SDM that focuses on education, training, and collaboration. To implement it requires implementation efforts on aspects of competence, formulation, and cooperation so that it can strengthen the human resources of Sulamadaha Coast managers.

KEYWORDS -SDM, Tourism, City of Ternate

I. INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector has become a field that has been widely developed by local governments. Because it is able to provide employment opportunities, economic growth in the area around tourist attractions, and contribute to local original income (Rusyidi&Fedryansah, 2018). The development of tourist attractions in the region is usually carried out by the government, private sector and local communities. However, in its development, it is often forgotten about the availability of human resources for management, thus affecting services for tourists (Bahri&Fitri, 2022; Sugiarto, &Mahagangga, 2020).

The existence of human resources in the tourism industry is very basic. Because tourism human resources are individuals, communities, groups and actors who manage each tourist attraction in a tourist area. The tourism industry is an activity that offers services, so it is necessary to adapt tourism services according to customer needs (Bahri&Fitri, 2022). Tourism human resources are also defined as all human aspects that support tourism activities, namely all human aspects that support tourism activities, both tangible and intangible, which aim to meet needs and create tourist satisfaction and have a positive impact on the economy, welfare and environmental and cultural sustainability in Indonesia (Darsana, &Koerniawaty, 2021).

According to Kristian (2017), tourist attraction management is an activity in organizing and managing the development activities of a tourism destination. Some examples of successful management of tourist attractions include WisaraNglanggeran Village which places young people as management actors (Yusuf, 2017), UmbulPongokKlaten Tourism Village (Kiswantor& Susanto (2019), and PujongKidul Malang tourist village (Ira, & Muhamad, 2020). This is because the process of managing tourist attractions opens up space for local communities to determine and implement various tourism services that suit the interests and needs of tourists. However, there are also many obstacles and obstacles faced by the government and local communities in managing tourist attractions. Mohbir (2023) & Asmara (2020) reveal that what regional governments face in running tourism services is the availability of competent human resources (HR).

Efforts to organize tourism services and human resources at Sulamadaha Beach, Ternate City have been carried out previously. Study conducted by Fabanyo&Sastrawan (2020); Putri, Malik, &Makarau (2022); and Muhammad et al, (2022) still focus on developing attractions, strengthening tourist guides, and strategies to increase tourist visits. Meanwhile, research on tourism human resources has also previously been carried out. Studies from Indriastuti&Ferdian (2020), Yulianah (2021), and Umasugi (2023) relate to human resources but focus on aspects of government programs, non-governmental organizations, and mapping human resource needs. Meanwhile, research reviewing models for strengthening human resources to manage marine tourism, especially Sulamadaha Beach, has not been carried out, so this study is very important in developing tourism human resources in Ternate City. So the aim of the research is to develop a model for strengthening human resources in supporting the management of the Sulamadaha Beach tourist attraction, Ternate City.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The case study approach in qualitative methods is an approach used to study certain phenomena or events in depth. In this approach, researchers will select one or several cases that are considered representative and relevant to study in detail. This case study approach aims to understand the context, processes and dynamics that occur in the case, as well as explore the various factors that influence the phenomenon or event. Qualitative methods allow researchers to obtain more in-depth and detailed data, because researchers will carry out observations, interviews and analysis of selected cases. Thus, the case study approach in qualitative methods can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon or event being studied. Data collection was carried out through interviews and documentation studies. Interviews were conducted directly with the manager of the Sulamadaha Beach tourist attraction. The data that has been taken is then analyzed through the stages of data sorting, data presentation, and drawing conclusions from the results of the analysis regarding strengthening human resources at Sulamadaha Beach.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Sulamadaha Beach Management Human Resources

Management of the Sulamadaha Beach tourist attraction is the authority of the Ternate City Government through the Tourism Office. In management practice, authority is delegated to the Sulamadaha Beach tourism awareness group (Pokdarwis). Pokdarwis is a form of institutional participation of local communities to get involved in tourism management. The formation of Pokdarwis was also facilitated by the Ternate City Tourism Office. This group is given the mandate to manage various tourist services related to aspects of tourist attractions, accommodation and accessibility at Sulamadaha Beach.

The organizational capacity of Pokdarwis can be mapped that this group consists of a chairman and several members. In terms of quantity, the number of members of the Sulamadaha Beach Pokdarwis is 10-15 people. They are divided into several areas of activity, namely cleanliness, security and culinary traders. Each has been given tasks in accordance with mutually agreed standard operating procedures. The cleaning department carries out the task of cleaning the tourist area in the morning and evening. The security department carries out the task of checking gazebos and busy spots when Sulamadaha Beach is crowded with tourists. This inspection aims to ensure that tourists do not do things that are prohibited in tourist areas, such as consuming alcohol which can disturb the comfort of other tourists. Meanwhile, the trading section serves various food and drink menus for visiting tourists.

The Tourism Office in the management of Sulamadaha Beach is related to the collection of entrance and parking ticket fees in the Sulamadaha Beach Area. The Tourism Office also facilitates various construction of facilities and infrastructure to support tourism activities at Sulamadaha Beach. Such as making gazebos, tourist attraction signboards, and information centers for tourists, as well as road access in the Sulamadaha Beach Area.

The stakeholders managing Sulamadaha Beach can be divided into two parts, namely from the Pokdarwis and the Tourism Office. This means that the two elements that are part of the management of Sulamadaha Beach above are parties that can be categorized as human resources in the management of Sulamadaha Beach. These parties are the ones who serve tourists while they are at Sulamadaha Beach and also

determine whether the service provided to tourists is good or not. Because the services provided by the parties above are the benchmark for determining the quality of tourism services received by tourists.

In connection with increasing the capacity of Sulamadaha Beach tourism managers in services for tourists, various parties have carried out this. The local government, through the Ternate City Tourism Office, is making efforts through various programs to increase the capacity of Sulamadaha Beach managers. Training was held for all tourism actors in Ternate City, including Sulamadaha Beach managers, with the aim of increasing knowledge for tourism actors, especially in relation to tourism services. Not only that, the North Maluku Province Tourism and Culture Office also conducted the same training to improve the quality of tourism services in Ternate City and North Maluku in general.

On the other hand, the involvement of higher education institutions in the Ternate City area in providing education to Sulamadaha Beach managers through community empowerment activities. As carried out by Khairun University through tourist guide training activities for Sulamadaha beach managers in 2022 (Muhammad, Hamka, & Mahmud, 2022). Apart from that, the involvement of universities in developing the capacity of Sulamadaha Beach managers is also carried out by the Ternate Open University in the format of providing tourism English training and an understanding of hospitality in tourism services (Malutcenter.com, 2023).

If we look at the qualifications of the management capacity of the Sulamadaha Beach tourist attraction, the average Pokdarwis member does not come from a tourism educational background. They are local residents who were recruited to be involved in managing tourist attractions through the institutionalization of Pokdarwis. However, this shows that tourism activities at Sulamadaha Beach have opened up space for local residents to participate in managing tourism activities. So that it reflects the application of the concept of sustainable tourism. However, community involvement has not been carried out comprehensively. This is inseparable from the ability of local communities to actively participate in tourism planning and development, which is limited by low community awareness and a lack of tourism knowledge and skills (Yuliantih, 2021). This condition shows that efforts are needed to continuously strengthen human resources for managers of the Sulamadaha Beach tourist attraction.

2. Discussion

The discourse on the role of human resources in developing tourist destinations has become a major concern for many groups. Garay, Lozano, & Malca, (2022) revealed that tourism activities have contributed to service provision activities, material and financial investment as well as human resources to meet the high demand for this sector. So competency development for tourism actors is very necessary to be able to meet the level of satisfaction expected by tourists.

Human resources have played an important role in the tourism industry. Tourism development in the region must pay serious attention to the aspect of human resources as the main element that supports various tourism activities. The role of human resources is believed to be able to provide improved service quality for tourists visiting tourist destinations. This is because tourism activities are related to hospitality services for tourists which are influenced by the abilities and competencies of tourism managers. So when the human resources who manage a tourist attraction are of high quality, the services provided to tourists will be too. So tourism is one of the sectors that provides the potential for diverse employment opportunities, as stated by Baum (2015) in his study that the global tourism industry has offered many choices of global workforce in the tourism sector from various levels and subsectors throughout the world.

Seeing this reality, it is necessary to encourage that human resource management in the tourism sector must be formalized in the form of training, education and personnel selection to test leadership skills, teamwork, communication and exchange of experience to implement innovative projects and gain competitive advantage. For this reason, collaboration between organizations is needed in order to contribute to sustainable human resource development in the tourism sector. So that the wide open potential for employment in the tourism sector can be utilized to bring prosperity to local communities.

The arguments put forward by Garay, Lozano, & Malca (2022) above are an important note for designing a model for strengthening human resources for managers of the Sulamadaha Beach tourist attraction, Ternate City. There are three things that can be underlined, namely competence, formalization and collaboration when strengthening human resources in the tourism sector. In the context of Sulamadaha Beach management, these three aspects can be used as a basis as a model for strengthening human resources to support the management of the Sulamadaha Beach tourist destination.

a. Competence

Competency for workers in the tourism sector is interpreted as the abilities and qualifications possessed by each individual or group engaged in tourism activities. Radjenovic (2018) explains that in meeting human resource needs in the tourism sector, it is necessary to pay attention to the influence of the following factors in compiling the competencies required in the tourism industry, namely: (a) employee qualification level, (b) employee age, (c) level employee motivation, (d) level of employee satisfaction and (e) training opportunities for employees. This means that recruiting employees in an institution that manages a tourism destination must use the considerations above so that it can support the quality of the employees' work in serving tourists.

Belias et al, (2017) also stated that strengthening human resources requires strategic leadership which aims to create an effective strategic planning process as well as employee recruitment, retention and professional development practices. As is done in the Greek tourism industry which has experienced a shift towards high quality services to customers that are competitive in the global tourism market.

If analyzed, the parties who manage Sulamadaha Beach do not meet the qualifications and competence in the tourism sector. Because educational background and experience are not yet related to the world of tourism. However, the tourism service process is still carried out by the manager. Because this management uses an empowerment paradigm. This means encouraging the involvement of local residents in managing tourism services by utilizing the potential of each individual. While strengthening the capacity of managers.

b. Formulation

The formulation aspect in strengthening human resources in the tourism sector is the steps taken to plan and implement an effective HR development strategy. In the tourism context, formulation involves analyzing workforce needs, determining development goals and targets, and planning appropriate training and development programs. To carry out this aspect, the role of Regional Government through the Tourism Office, educational institutions and tourism industry organizations is really needed. However, local governments have an important role in formulating policies and regulations that support human resource development in the tourism industry. Educational institutions, such as universities and tourism schools, are responsible for providing education and training programs that meet industry needs. Indriastuti (2020) said that the role of the government (Tourism Service) is to be an actor in coaching, mentoring and providing support for tourist destination managers.

The formulation for strengthening special human resources for the management of Sulamadaha Beach has not specifically been designed by the management and regional government. So far, only training has been carried out for all tourism managers in Ternate City. So a formulation design regarding strengthening human resources for the management of Sulamadaha Beach is really needed. This is to support strengthening management capacity and sustainability of tourism services at Sulamadaha Beach that are quality and oriented to the needs of tourists.

c. Collaboration

In supporting the development of tourism human resources, it is necessary to pay attention to collaboration between the parties. Katunian (2019) said that sustainable human resource development is needed which focuses on cooperation between parties in the tourism industry at large. This means that there is cooperation between parties such as tourism companies, government, public institutions, educational institutions

and international organizations in developing human resources. Thus, this collaboration can contribute to the sustainable development of human resources in the tourism sector.

Katunian also added that the next phase that needs to be carried out by the government as a regulator and supervisor is to design a model of cooperation between the parties. Usually collaboration initiatives initiated by the government will be followed by the parties. Yuliantih (2021) also said the same thing that participation from the government and non-governmental organizations is needed to participate in developing and increasing the capacity of human resources for tourism object managers. On the other hand, Soseilissa&Seipalla (2021) reminded that if there is no collaboration in efforts to develop tourism human resources, it will cause obstacles and less than optimal development of various tourist attraction products.

In the context of managing Sulamadaha Beach, there has been collaboration in strengthening human resources. However, a collaboration process is formed naturally between managers and universities through empowerment activities. There has not been a collaborative design plan between the parties in strengthening human resources prepared by the regional government. So joint initiation is really needed to encourage collaboration in strengthening human resources. Collaboration between parties can create strong synergies to increase the capacity of tourism managers who are able to support tourist experiences.

IV. CONCLUSION

In developing tourism in the region, human resource elements must be considered. Tourism services can depend on competence, formulation and collaboration. When these three components are developed sustainably, they can help the tourism service process so that tourists feel better when visiting a tourism destination. This research produces a model for strengthening human resources at Sulamadaha Beach which is based on the three previous components.

REFERENCES

- [1] Asmara, S. (2020). Tinjauan Kritis Kendala dan Dampak Pengembangan Pariwisata Indonesia. *Prosiding Webinar Fakultas Ekonomi Unimed "Strategi Dunia Usaha Menyikapi Status Indonesia Sebagai Negara Maju: Pra dan Pasca Covid-19"*, 140-151.
- [2] Bahri, A. S., & Fitri, A. (2022). Potensi Sumber Daya Manusia Bidang Pariwisata Di Kawasan Strategis Pariwisata Nasional Labuan Bajo, Nusa Tenggara Timur. *Jurnal Hospitaliti & Pariwisata*, 3, 84-92.
- [3] Baum, T. (2015). Human Resources In Tourism: Still Waiting For Change?—A 2015 reprise. *Tourism Management*, 50, 204-212.
- [4] Belias, D., Trivellas, P., Koustelios, A., Serdaris, P., Varsanis, K., & Grigoriou, I. (2017). Human Resource Management, Strategic Leadership Development And The Greek Tourism Sector. In *Tourism, Culture and Heritage in a Smart Economy: Third International Conference IACuDiT, Athens 2016* (pp. 189-205). Springer International Publishing.
- [5] Darsana, I. M., & Koerniawaty, F. T. (2021). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Personality, Budaya Organisasi Dan Kinerja Karyawan, Aplikasi Pada Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Ke-pariwisataan*. Nilacakra.
- [6] Fabanyo, A. A., & Sastrawan, I. A. (2020). Upaya Dinas Pariwisata Ternate Dalam Mengatasi Penurunan Kunjungan Wisatawan Di Daya Tarik Wisata Pantai Sulamadaha. *Jurnal Destinasi Pariwisata*, 8(2), 212-217.
- [7] Garay, J. P. P., Lozano, R. A. R., & Malca, W. F. B. (2022). Management of Human Resources In Results of The System of The Mypes of The Tourism Sector. *Science, Education and Innovations in The Context Of Modern Problems*, 5(3).
- [8] Indriastuti, W. A., & Ferdian, N. (2020). Peran Dinas Pariwisata dalam Mengembangkan Sumber Daya Manusia di Objek Wisata Candi Sukuh Kabupaten Karanganyar. *Mabha Jurnal*, 1(1), 83-103.
- [9] Ira, W. S., & Muhamad, M. (2020). Partisipasi Masyarakat Pada Penerapan Pembangunan Pariwisata Berkelanjutan (Studi Kasus Desa Wisata Pujon Kidul, Kabupaten Malang). *Jurnal Pariwisata Terapan*, 3(2), 124-135.
- [10] Katunian, A. (2019). Sustainability As A New Approach For The Human Resource Development In Tourism Sector. *Viešoji politika ir administravimas*, 18(4), 405-417.
- [11] Kiswanto, A., & Susanto, D. R. (2019). Pengaruh Sarana dan Prasarana Pendukung Wisata Terhadap Kepuasan Wisatawan di Umbul Ponggok, Klaten. *Khasanah Ilmu-Jurnal Pariwisata Dan Budaya*, 10(2), 106-112.

-
- [12] Kristian, Y. (2017). Pengelolaan Objek Wisata Oleh Dinas Pariwisata Kabupaten Kutai Barat Di Danau Aco Kampung Linggang Melapeh, Kecamatan Linggang Bigung. *E-journal Administrasi Negara*, 5(1), 5404-5417.
- [13] Malutcenter.com. (2023). Perkuat SDM Pariwisata, Universitas Terbuka Gelar PKM di Sulamadaha. <https://malutcenter.com/2023/09/03/perkuat-sdm-pariwisata-universitas-terbuka-gelar-pkm-di-sulamadaha/>
- [14] Muhammad, I., Hamka, N., & Mahmud, N. (2022). Pelatihan Pemandu Wisata (Guide) Di Pantai Sulamadaha Dan Jikomalamo Kecamatan Kota Ternate Utara. *Akrab Juara: Jurnal Ilmu-ilmu Sosial*, 7(4), 292-299.
- [15] Putri, J. F. A., Malik, A. A., & Makarau, V. H. (2022). Pengembangan Objek Wisata Pantai Sulamadaha Di Kota Ternate. *Spasial*, 9(2), 219-229.
- [16] Radjenovic, M. (2018). The Quality Of Human Resources In Tourism And Hospitality Industry In Montenegro. *Transformations in Business & Economics*, 17(2).
- [17] Rusyidi, B., & Fedryansah, M. (2018). Pengembangan Pariwisata Berbasis Masyarakat. *Focus: Jurnal Pekerjaan Sosial*, 1(3), 155-165.
- [18] Soselissa, F., & Seipalla, B. (2021). Peran Stakeholders dalam Pengelolaan Objek Wisata Alam Siwang Paradise di Desa Siwang Kota Ambon. *Jurnal hutan pulau-pulau kecil*, 5(1), 28-39.
- [19] Sugiarto, A., & Mahagangga, I. G. A. O. (2020). Kendala Pengembangan Pariwisata di Destinasi Pariwisata Labuan Bajo Nusa Tenggara Timur (Studi kasus komponen produk pariwisata). *Jurnal Destinasi Pariwisata*, 8(2), 18-25.
- [20] Umasugi, M. (2023). Pemetaan Kebutuhan Sumber Daya Manusia Dalam Pengelolaan Kawasan Ekowisata Nusliko, Halmahera Tengah. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen, Ekonomi, & Akuntansi (MEA)*, 7(1), 100-116.
- [21] Yulianah, Y. (2021). Mengembangkan Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Pariwisata Berbasis Komunitas di Pedesaan. *Komitmen: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen*, 2(1), 1-9.